

Color outside the map

a short four-color map proof proposal

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1 Abstract

We generate all maps of size $m + 1$ by adding all valid new regions to all maps of size m . Using four colors, we color a new region with colors different from adjacent regions. We generate a set of all valid border colorings for each map and decompose these into *bundles* of *fiber* sets, each associated with a unique *handle*, and show by complete induction that all fiber sets are *colorable*.

2 Introduction

The four-color map theorem, which states that all planar maps can be colored using just four colors, has an interesting history. It was first documented by Guthrie [1]. Kempe [2] published the first proof attempt, using alternating-color paths (Kempe chains). Heawood [3] later proved Kempe's proof to be false. The first valid proof was found only a century later by Appel and Haken [4, 5]. This is when we became familiar with this theorem. It used a computer program to find 1,936 unavoidable reducible configurations. While the crux of this proof was elegant, it was controversial because reliable verification was difficult until another computer program was developed for that purpose [8]. Robertson et al. [7] published a shorter version of the Appel–Haken proof, reducing it to 633 configurations. All past proofs are graph-based and concentrate on the structural properties of these graphs. In this paper, we concentrate on the border of maps instead.

3 Definitions

We represent a colored map by its border segments: a circular sequence (or necklace) of colors. In the illustrations we use red, green, orange, and blue. In the text we use:

$$C = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$$

Figure 1: a border coloring

The set of all valid border colorings is

$$R_n = \{ \langle c_0, \dots, c_{n-1} \rangle \in C^n \mid c_i \neq c_{(i+1) \bmod n} \}$$

Angle brackets denote circularity. A map with border size n has a coloring set

$$E_n \subset R_n$$

Note that since E_n is a set of necklaces, rotating and or reversing its colorings by k does not change its structure. In this paper we won't make use of this isomorphism. Indices should be interpreted modulo n to allow for wrapping around the first element of the coloring.

We now work towards decomposing coloring sets into *bundles*, each bundle consisting of a *handle* and a set of *fibers*. See the figure (in the induction step paragraph) of a coloring set and several of its decompositions into bundles.

The boundaries of a coloring with length n are

$$B_n = \{ b \mid b \in \{0, \dots, n-1\} \}$$

with i the boundary between segments i and $i+1$.

A *part* is a sub list of a coloring with length l . Valid lengths are

$$L_n = \{ l \mid l \in \{0, \dots, n-2\} \}$$

We will not be using parts of length $n-1$ or n , due to *triangulation* restrictions to be discussed later. So, a part is

$$p_{b,l}(c) = (c_b, \dots, c_{b+l-1}), b \in B, l \in L$$

and its complement (the superscript c denotes complement)

$$p_{b,l}^c(c) = (c_{b+l}, \dots, c_{b-1}), b \in B, l \in L$$

A *fiber* and *handle* of coloring c for a given b and l

$$\begin{aligned} f &= p_{b,l}(c) \\ h &= f^c \end{aligned}$$

The set of handles of E for a given b and l is

$$H = \{p_{b,l}^c(c) \mid c \in E\}$$

The set of fibers associated with handle h (b denotes b right shifts)

$$F_h = \{f \mid \sigma^b(f \cdot h) \in E\}$$

A bundle for a given b and l is a tuple of a handle with its associated fibers

$$\beta = (F_h, h), h \in H$$

The coloring subset from which β originated is

$$E_\beta = \bigcup_{f \in \pi(\beta)} \sigma^b(f \cdot \pi^2(\beta))$$

(π^1, π^2 denote the tuple members). Because E and E_β are structurally equivalent,

$$E_\beta \cong \beta$$

All bundles for E and a given b and l are

$$\mathcal{B}_{b,l} = \{(F_h, h) \mid h \in H\}$$

Note that E can be recomposed from this bundle set

$$E = \{\sigma^b(f \cdot h) \mid f \in F_h, h \in H, (h, F_h) \in \mathcal{B}_{b,l}\}$$

Therefore, E and its bundle set are isomorphic:

$$E_\beta \cong \beta$$

The union of all bundle sets of E for all valid b and l is

$$\Phi_E = \bigcup_{b=0}^{n-1} \bigcup_{l=0}^{n-2} \mathcal{B}_{b,l}$$

4 Induction hypothesis

$$\mathcal{H}_m : \forall E \in \mathcal{C}_m \forall \mathcal{B} \in \Phi_E \forall c \in C \exists f \in \pi(\mathcal{B}) : c \notin f$$

with \mathcal{C}_m the set of border colorings of all maps with m regions. In other words, all fiber sets have at least one fiber without red, one without green, one without orange, and one without blue. We call the fiber sets *colorable*.

Figure 2: a base map coloring for E

5 Induction base

We build border maps with border size 3. The induction base therefore is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}_3 &= \{E\} \\ E &= \{(1, 2, 3), \dots, (4, 3, 2)\} \end{aligned}$$

E is the border coloring set for the sole map with 3 regions. The colorings are a permutation of 3 colors out 4, for a total of $4!$ colorings. Note that $E = R_3$.

E 's fiber sets

$$\Phi_3 = \{\{(c_0), (c_1)\} \mid (c_0, c_1) \in \mathcal{C}, c_0 \neq c_1\}$$

In each fiber set, one fiber lacks three colors, the other a different set of three colors, therefore all four colors are lacking in at least one fiber.

$$\implies \mathcal{H}_3 \text{ holds}$$

6 Induction step

We generate a new E' by adding a new region to a coloring set E . An addition is defined by a tuple (b, l) . All valid additions are

$$\mathcal{A} = \{(b, l) \mid b \in \mathbf{B}_n, l \in L_n\}$$

In other words, all fibers at index b with length l are replaced with the new segment's color s iff s is different from the colors in the fiber and its neighbors, thus producing a valid coloring. Additions are restricted such that a new segment starts and ends between, and not on, boundaries, form a contiguous connection,

Figure 3: a new segment covering some old segments

Figure 4: the new border coloring

and do not cover more than $n - 2$ segments. These restrictions guarantee that all colorings produced represent map *triangulations*. If all triangulations can be colored with four colors, then so can all maps [4, 5]. The size of a new coloring c' produced from c is

$$|c'| = |c| - l + 1, c' \in E', c \in E$$

The colorings for all maps of $m + 1$ regions are

$$\mathbb{C}_{m+1} = \{\alpha(E) \mid a \in \mathcal{A}, E \in \mathbb{C}_{\uparrow}\}$$

We now show by means of reductio ad absurdum that the induction hypothesis holds. Assume there is a fiber set that is *not* colorable:

$$\exists_{E' \in \mathbb{C}_{m+1}} \exists_{B' \in \Phi_{E'}} \exists_{c \in C} \forall_{f \in \pi B'} : c \in f$$

In preparation, we discuss nested fiber sets. A bundle's fiber set itself can be decomposed into smaller bundles, which can be decomposed further. We could thus create an hierarchy of ever smaller bundles, like Russian dolls. We could also go in the other direction: start with bundles with long handles and small fiber sets, and decompose the handles into smaller handles with larger fibers, already decomposed.

Figure 5: an E_{13} and some decompositions

For illustration purposes, figure 5(a) shows a (conveniently ordered coloring set) E_{13} . 5(b) shows E_{13} decomposed into bundles with short fibers. 5(d) shows E_{13} decomposed into bundles with longer fibers. The decomposition of 5(c) is

a nested one: the longer fibers are decomposed into bundles with the same sets of short fibers as in the second decomposition. This nesting can be produced either by starting with the sets of long fibers, working inward, or the sets of short fibers, working outward. The set of sets with short fibers is identical regardless of whether decomposition happens inward or outward. E can be reproduced by re-composition from any of the three bundle sets in the figure. The counter example fiber set F' is not colorable:

$$\mathcal{B}' = (F_{h'}, h')$$

$$\exists_{c \in C} \forall_{f \in F'} c \in f$$

Assume F' is located at index b' and is l' long. There are two cases:

1. the new segment $s \in F'$
2. the new segment $s \notin F'$ (but in the handle h' of F')

Case 1 The bundle in E from which F' originated is

$$\beta = (F_{h'}, h'), \beta \in \Phi_E \implies F_{h'} \text{ colorable}$$

$F_{h''}$ can be further decomposed into bundles

$$h_2 \cdot F_{h_1, h_2} \cdot h_1$$

with

$$h_2 = (c_{b'}, \dots, c_{b'-1})$$

$$f = (c_b, \dots, c_{b+l-1}), f \in F_{h_1 h_2}$$

$$h_1 = (c_{b+l}, \dots, c_{b'+l'+l-1})$$

We pick a color c and a decomposed bundle such that

$$c \notin h_1 \cdot h_2$$

and extend the handle of $F_{h'}$ with the handle of one of the decomposed bundles,

$$h'' = h_1 \cdot h' \cdot h_2$$

and we create

$$\beta'' = (F_{h''}, h'')$$

$$\beta'' \in \Phi_E \implies F_{h''} \text{ is colorable}$$

Fig. 5 illustrates this: see the right and middle decompositions. These nested fiber sets are identical to the fiber sets produced by decomposing F directly at (b, l) . We will now add segment s to $F_{h''}$. Since $F_{h''}$ is colorable, *it does not exclude any candidate colors for the new segment*. This is the crux of the

induction step. Colors of h'' adjacent to s are not valid however, so at least two valid colors remain. This produces two fibers for F'' (three if $c_{b-1} = c_{b+l+1}$.)

$$h_2 \cdot s_1 \cdot h_1$$

$$h_2 \cdot s_2 \cdot h_1$$

Since $c \notin h_1 \cdot h_2$ and either $s_1 \neq c$ or $s_2 \neq c$, one of the fibers of E' must also lack color c . Therefore, the counter argument for case 1 is false:

$$\implies F' \text{ is colorable}$$

Figure 6 illustrates colorable nested fiber sets. Red indicates red is lacking, green indicates green is lacking, orange indicates orange is lacking, blue indicates blue is lacking, and black means all colors are present.

Figure 6: illustration of induction step case 1

Case 2 This case is trivial. Exchange the new segment with the fiber it replaced. The resulting bundle is one of the bundles in E , thus the counter argument for case 2 is false as well,

$$\implies F' \text{ is colorable}$$

Conclusion In both cases, the counter argument is false,

$$\implies \mathcal{H}_{\uparrow+\infty} \langle \uparrow \downarrow \uparrow \rangle$$

and the induction is complete

QED

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